

Stability Study of Some Complexes of Vanillin Sulphanilate (Van-Sul)

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The interactions of certain transition metal ions Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Mn(II) with vanillin-sulphanilate (Van-Sul) have been studied in 20% ethanol-water medium at different temperatures and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength following Irving-Rossotti pH titration technique. The stepwise proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants ($\log K_n^H$ and $\log K_n$), calculated using various computational methods, show the order of stability as Fe(III) > Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Mn(II). Thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS), calculated at 30° and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength, show that the interaction of Van-Sul and these metal ions is chelation-reaction between ionic species. Thus, the entropy change plays important role in giving the observed stability.

RECENTLY, interest has developed in metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from aromatic hydroxy aldehyde and amino acids, as their study provides valuable information about biological transamination reactions and metal pyridoxal amino acid systems¹⁻³. Among several such compounds are the metal complexes of the Schiff bases derived from vanillin⁴⁻⁹. In continuation of our studies¹⁰ on the metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from vanillin, the present study deals with the potentiometric determination of proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Mn(II) complexes with a Schiff base derived by the condensation of vanillin and sulphanilic acid.

Experimental

The preparation and characteristics of the ligand, Van-Sul, are described earlier^{10(a)}.

All the reagents employed were of high purity. The preparation and standardisation of the metal ion solutions and the experimental details are the same as reported elsewhere^{10(b)}.

Stoichiometry of the complexes was ascertained by potentiometric (pH) and conductometric titrations. The Bjerrum-Calvin¹¹ pH titration technique as modified by Irving-Rossotti¹² was followed to determine the proton-ligand and the metal-ligand formation constants. For this, the following three solutions keeping the total volume 50 ml with 1 : 4 (v/v) ethanol-water as solvent, were titrated against carbonate free 0.1 M KOH in the same solvent medium at different temperatures (30 and 40°):

- 5 ml 0.1 M HNO₃,
- solution (a) + 10 ml 0.01 M ligand solution,
- solution (b) + 5 ml 0.002 M metal solution.

The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1 M in each case by adding appropriate quantities of 1.0 M KNO₃. Correction of pH for 20% ethanol-water system was done as described by VanUitert and Hass¹³ and Irving and Rossotti¹². A graph of pH vs volume of alkali added was plotted. The three titration curves were referred as (a) acid titration curve, (b) ligand titration curve and (c) metal titration curve.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand formation constants, $\log K_n^H$:

The values of \bar{n}_A , the average number of protons associated with the ligand, at various pH were calculated using Irving-Rossotti equation¹². Calculations of proton ligand formation constants, $\log K_n^H$, was carried out by (a) the half integral method (from the plot of \bar{n}_A vs pH), (b) the pointwise calculation method and (c) the linear plot method¹². The results obtained by the three methods at 30 and

Fig. 1. Proton-ligand stability constants.
—○—30° —●—40°.

40° are recorded in Table 1 (Fig. 1) and are found to be in agreement.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS
log K_n^H , of Van-Sul at 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength

	30°	40°	Method
log K_1^H	7.70	7.95	a
	7.70	7.97	b
	7.62 (7.70)	7.97 (7.97)	c
log K_2^H	2.85	2.77	a
	2.87	2.65	b
	3.23 (2.90)	2.77 (2.75)	c
log β_2^H	10.55	10.72	a
	10.57	10.62	b
	10.85 (10.60)	10.74 (10.72)	c

a—Half integral method ; b—Linear plot method ;
c—Pointwise calculated method.

The maximum value of $\bar{n}A$ obtained (~ 2) indicates two replaceable hydrogens in a molecule of Van-Sul.

Metal-ligand formation constants, log K_n :

Conductometric titrations (Fig. 2) carried out using monovariation method¹⁴ indicate formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes. The maximum value of \bar{n} (Fig. 3) in all the cases was found ~ 2 . This also confirms the formation of only two complexes, (ML and ML₂), in the systems studied.

The stepwise stability constants of the metal complexes, log K_1 and log K_2 , were recorded directly from the formation curves (\bar{n} vs pL), (Fig. 3). The refined values for the same were computed by the method of least square and are given in Table 2. The formation curves in many

Fig. 2. Conductometric titrations, Van-Sul systems.
[A] Mn(II), [B] Co(II), [C] Cu(II), [D] Fe(III) and [E] Ni(II).

Fig. 3. Formation curves, Van-Sul systems.
—○—30°, —○—40°, [A] Mn(II), [B] Co(II),
[C] Ni(II), [D] Cu(II) and [E] Fe(III).

TABLE 2—STEPWISE FORMATION CONSTANTS OF
VAN-SUL COMPLEXES
 $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KNO₃)

Metal ions	30°			40°		
	log K_1	log K_2	log β_2	log K_1	log K_2	log β_2
Fe(III)	8.84	6.61	15.45	10.07	6.73	16.10
Cu(II)	8.20	2.82	11.01	8.58	2.84	11.42
Ni(II)	7.36	3.56	10.92	7.64	3.61	11.25
Co(II)	6.58	3.97	10.55	6.86	4.02	10.88
Mn(II)	4.47	3.51	7.98	4.68	3.63	8.81

cases (Fig. 3) could not touch \bar{n} values below 0.5. Hence the value of log K_1 in such cases have been obtained by the method of least square.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The values of the stepwise and overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy of complexation reactions at 30° and 0.1 M ionic strength with KNO₃ were calculated by using standard equations¹⁴. The values are tabulated in Table 3.

The value of $\bar{n}A$ in the proton-ligand formation curve (Fig. 1) varies between 0.3 and 1.8. Similarly, the equivalents of alkali per mole of the ligand used in the ligand titration is more than one. Both the observations indicate two successive steps of acid dissociation of the ligand. These two equilibria correspond with the two inflections in the ligand titration curve, one at pH 2.8 and the other at pH 7.7. The first one is associated with the removal of proton from $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group, while the second for the removal of the phenolic hydrogen.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE FORMATION OF VAN-SUL COMPLEXES
 $\mu = 0.1 M (KNO_3)$; Temp. = 30°

Metal ions	Free energy change*			Enthalpy change*			Entropy change**		
	$-\Delta G_1$	$-\Delta G_2$	$-\Delta G$	ΔH_1	ΔH_2	ΔH	ΔS_1	ΔS_2	ΔS
Fe(III)	12.34	9.22	21.56	53.46	5.62	59.09	217.2	48.9	266.1
Cu(II)	11.48	3.95	15.39	16.40	0.60	17.01	92.0	15.0	106.9
Ni(II)	10.27	4.97	15.25	12.25	.19	14.44	74.8	23.6	97.9
Co(II)	9.18	5.54	14.73	12.00	2.08	14.08	69.9	25.1	95.1
Mn(II)	6.23	4.90	11.13	9.28	5.25	14.53	51.2	33.5	84.7

* kcal/mole ; ** cal/deg/mole

The values of proton ligand constants, $\log K_n^H$, particularly $\log K_1^H$, (Table 1) at 40° are slightly higher than that at 30°. This shows less ionisation of the ligand particularly the phenolic hydrogen at higher temperature. This observation is similar to that seen in case of Van-An^{10(b)}, a Schiff base prepared by condensing vanillin with anthranilic acid.

The nature of the pH titration curves in case of the mixtures (b) and (c) indicates the liberation of one equivalent of acid per mole of the ligand below pH 6, both in the absence and in the presence of the metal ions. Thus, the first step acid dissociation of the ligand (i.e. deprotonation of the SO₃H group) was not influenced by the metal ions. Therefore, the SO₃H group is not involved in the interaction of Van-Sul with these metal ions. Analysis of the titration data in the pH range 6 to 9.5 according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹² showed that for the association of each mole of the ligand species to a metal ion one equivalent of acid per gram ion of the metal was liberated. Therefore, from a consideration of the pK_{OH} value of the ligand (Table 1) and the pH range of the buffer region in the metal titration curves, stepwise chelation of metal ion with the ligand ions may be assumed to take place through deprotonation of the phenolic OH group.

Further, an analysis of the formation curves (Fig. 3) indicates that the addition of Van-Sul molecules to the metal ions takes place stepwise in such a way that the formation of the two species is independent of each other. Firstly, one atom of the metal combines with one molecule of Van-Sul. The 1 : 1 complex thus formed does not appreciably combine with a second molecule of Van-Sul to give 1 : 2 complex until at least more than 80% of the 1 : 1 complex has been formed. This is similar to that observed in case of Van-An^{10(b)} and amino acids¹⁵.

The order of stability obtained (Table 2) for these metal complexes shows that Van-Sul also exhibits the same sequence of avidity for these metal ions as possessed by Van-An¹⁰ and the amino acids¹⁵, Fe(III) > Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Mn(II). This is the order according to the Irving-Williams series¹⁶ and the empirical rules given by them¹⁷. However, the values of stability constants for these Van-Sul complexes are much higher than those obtained for the corresponding Van-An complexes^{10(b)}. The

higher values of stability constants for the Van-Sul complexes are in accordance with its higher pK_a value and seems quite expected when the pH of complexation is considered. Van-Sul molecule adds to the metal ions at pH ~ 6 involving its phenolic OH group, while Van-An complexes does so at pH ~ 4 utilising its carboxyl group (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4

The thermodynamic parameters show that these reactions are endothermic and entropy supported. The higher values of free energy change (ΔG) (Table 3) at higher temperature (40°) indicate clearly that the rate of the reaction increases with increase in temperature. It is further seen that the values of enthalpy change (ΔH) are positive in all the cases indicating energy absorption during chelate formation. The values of entropy change (ΔS) accompanying the formation of complexes (Table 3) are very high and positive. As a result of this, the entropy term strongly favours the complex formation and accordingly chelation effect is essentially an entropy effect. The very high entropy change is also justified by considering the greater availability of coordination sites on these metal ions, which are being released during chelation.

References

1. A. L. LEHNINGER, "Biochemistry", Butterworth Publishers, New York, 1975.
2. D. E. METZLER and E. E. SNELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 979.
3. D. E. METZLER, M. IKAWA and E. E. SNELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 648.
4. W. U. MALIK, R. BEMBI and SUSHILA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 776.
5. W. U. MALIK, R. BEMBI and SUSHILA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 762.
6. J. CHACKO and G. PARAMESWARAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 95.
7. M. S. PATEL, T. TRIVEDI and D. N. VYAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 353; 1979, **56**, 126.
8. T. TRIVEDI, M. S. PATEL and D. N. VYAS, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 231.
9. O. P. ARORA, S. N. MISHRA and M. P. BHUTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 273.

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10. P. KHANNA and P. B. CHAKRAWARTI, (a) *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 828 ; (b) *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Communicated.
11. A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, "Chemistry of Metal Chelate Compounds", Printice Hall, N. Y., 1953, p. 192.
12. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
13. L. G. VANUITERT and O. HASS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 8651.
14. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASIL'EV, "Instability Constants of Complex Compounds", Pergamon Press, London, p. 59.
15. A. ALBERT, *Biochem. J.*, 1950, **47**, 531.
16. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746.
17. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.